

FAIR Principles Baseline Comments

A FAIRsFAIR WP4 Discussion Document

Introduction	2
The FAIR Guiding Principles	3
To be Findable:	3
F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	3
F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	5
F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	6
F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	7
To be Accessible:	7
A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	8
A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	9
A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	10
A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	10
To be Interoperable:	11
I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	12
I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	13
I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	14
To be Reusable:	15
R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	15
R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	16
R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	17
R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	18

Introduction

In the early stages of the FAIRsFAIR Project it became clear that the same comments and questions related to the FAIR Principles were being raised by many of those undertaking related work. In March 2020 members of the project prepared a commentary on the 'baseline' issues with the FAIR Principles to be used as a common reference point for addressing challenges and monitoring change. Since then there has been a great deal of work around FAIR including the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model: Specification and Guidelines¹ of indicators designed to support testing against the Principles. Within FAIRsFAIR there has been work on policy-level engagement², support for achieving CoreTrustSeal³, metrics and tests for object FAIRness⁴, and a capability maturity model for CoreTrustSeal FAIR enabling⁵ practice.

Despite the enormous progress, it is acknowledged that we are still on a journey towards FAIR data and FAIR enabling repositories. After the FAIRsFAIR project, future challenges include further work on community standards, metrics development, assessment systems and the disciplinary side of FAIR.

The FAIR Principles define that data and metadata (digital objects) should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The CoreTrustSeal answer to the question "by whom" will be 'the defined designated community of users'. But automated testing at scale requires evidence that is also machine-interpretable.

A number of the FAIR Principles' items for clarification in this document relate to 'natural language' terms that require clarification and specification to support machine actionability. But this challenge also extends to the content of metadata schemas where the interpretation of common elements, e.g. date, may be underspecified or implemented in different ways by different users of the schemas.

This text seeks to consider the issues around the FAIR Data Principles, particularly as they apply to the notion of a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR). We can progress without all of these questions being addressed, but clarifying them will ensure a better overall solution.

Monospaced text in the following part of the document is taken from <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>⁶ though it is noted that there is some small

¹ <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

² D3.1 FAIR Policy Landscape Analysis <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5537032>

³ Certification + FAIR Support Workshop for Data Repositories - addressing common issues in CoreTrustSeal self-assessments <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4282444>

⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-ujj-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

⁵ D4.6 Report on a maturity model towards FAIR data in FAIR repositories, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090388>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

variance in the publically available instances of the FAIR Principles⁷. Text in the tables is taken from the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group Indicators⁸ and from the FAIRsFAIR Metrics and associated practical tests⁹ that have been developed since the first version of this paper was released. Where terms from the Principles would benefit from clarification to support implementation they are listed, preceded by ‘Clarify:’

The FAIR Guiding Principles

To be Findable:

F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
<p>RDA-F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier (Essential)</p> <p>RDA-F1-01D Data is identified by a persistent identifier (Essential)</p>	<p>FsF-F1-01D Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The object is identified by an unique identifier (GUID¹⁰ or IRI¹¹) that follows a proper syntax. • The identifier is web-accessible (not broken).
<p>RDA-F1-02M Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier (Essential)</p> <p>RDA-F1-02D Data is identified by a globally unique identifier (Essential)</p>	<p>FsF-F1-02D Data is assigned a persistent identifier.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A data identifier is specified based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme and syntax suitable for research data. • The identifier is web-accessible, i.e., it resolves to a landing page with metadata of the data object.

In many repositories, the data and metadata are defined together as a single digital object with a single identifier. The FAIRsFAIR metric focuses on a single ‘data’ identifier and the associated practical tests provide a specific list of criteria for evaluation.

⁷ FAIR Comparison: A Tabular Comparison of Publicly Available Versions of the FAIR Data Principles, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5946810>

⁸ FAIR Data Maturity Model: Specification and Guidelines, <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

⁹ D4.5 Report on FAIR Data Assessment Toolset and Badging Scheme, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336159>

¹⁰ <https://www.techtarget.com/searchwindowsserver/definition/GUID-global-unique-identifier>

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internationalized_Resource_Identifier

Persistent Identifier services such as DataCite¹², which support the creation and resolution of identifiers and their submission and management can provide assurances that identifiers are globally unique. But they can only provide a system which supports persistence, they cannot guarantee it. Persistence in terms of maintained metadata and resolution to the correct object remains dependent on those responsible for managing the digital objects. When repositories are seeking to enable this principle, their persistent identifier service providers share some responsibility in providing evidence for uniqueness and for best practices in enabling and ensuring persistence.

The FAIRsFAIR practical test checks that a “data identifier is specified based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme and syntax suitable for research data”. Since no authoritative list of valid persistent identifiers yet exists, the test uses the DataCite identifier type vocabulary¹³ (DataCite Metadata Working Group 2019), these and those identifiers listed in <https://identifiers.org> are considered to be persistent since they are managed and maintained, ensuring compliance with the EOSC PID policy¹⁴.

Adopting some popular persistent identifier (PID) provider solution will be a common repository approach. Whereas we don't yet have global community agreement, the European PID policy gives some advice on minimal standards for designing and managing globally unique identifiers capable of being updated indefinitely to resolve to the correct (meta)data object. As no 'approved' list of providers exists, it may not be appropriate for CoreTrustSeal to reject an applicant that provided evidence for an effective local system acceptable to their designated community.

Repositories not using a 'recognised' persistent identifier service may be able to offer assurances that their own identifiers are unique and that their procedures ensure persistence. But they must provide evidence for this and could be expected to do so in more detail than a repository using a 'well known' PID service.

Granular identifiers may also be assigned to 'parts' of an object including files or structures within a file (one identifier per variable for instance). We must not assume that local assumptions about 'object models' are universal.

Clarify: **persistent?**

Do we envisage standard criteria for PID providers and a registry of those that comply? Who would define standards and carry out assessments?

¹² <https://doi.org/>

¹³ https://schema.datacite.org/archive/kernel-2.2/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v2.2.pdf

¹⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R., et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
F2 RDA-F2-01M Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery (Essential)	FsF-F2-01M Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some metadata (at all) has been made available via common (web) standards. • Minimum core citation metadata is specified (creator, title, publication date, publisher, and identifier) • Minimum core descriptive metadata is specified (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) through appropriate metadata fields.

The FAIRsFAIR metric proposes an initial list of essential descriptive metadata elements based on previously defined standards and best practices such as the OAIS¹⁵ reference model, data citation recommendations (e.g. ESIP¹⁶, FORCE11¹⁷) and domain agnostic standards. The practical test includes a requirement that “Some metadata []has been made available via common (web) standards”, reflecting a dependency on common protocols for exposing digital object information to enable automated testing at scale.

There are further challenges here in developing clear requirements and defining acceptable evidence. Richness is clearly desirable but challenging to define, or to quantify even at a general level. If particular metadata standards are to be deemed ‘rich enough’ (e.g. for a particular data type or discipline) this implies a need for community consensus and/or some form of authoritative body and perhaps a metadata standard registry¹⁸ that defines which standards and which levels of ‘richness’ are sufficient. Well recognised domain agnostic

¹⁵ Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS), book, June 2012
<https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>

¹⁶ ESIP Data Preservation and Stewardship Committee. 2019. Data Citation Guidelines for Earth Science Data. Ver. 2. Earth Science Information Partners. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8441816>

¹⁷ Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Martone M. (ed.) San Diego CA: FORCE11; 2014 <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egykh>

¹⁸ <https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>

metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core, DCAT) consistently propose a comparatively small number of descriptors to define the basic requirements for metadata. It will be necessary to reach consensus on whether these can be considered sufficiently 'rich' at a general level, and how they may be extended for disciplinary purposes.

See related comments under R1.

Clarify: **rich**?

F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier for the data (Essential)	FsF-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content• Check if the identifier (link) to access data content is included in the metadata and test if the content identifier is active.

One implication here is that the metadata and the data it describes may be different 'objects' in different locations. There is a clear need to be able to find/resolve/locate the data *from* its metadata.

An identifier might be buried in prose and therefore unclear, or it may not be explicit that an identifier string is to the associated data (e.g. if there are numerous identifiers in the metadata). An identifier in bold at the top of the record might be sufficient for a human, but a machine might require an identifier bound in appropriately defined structural metadata elements.

The FAIRsFAIR practical tests have a clear dependency on standardised and machine actionable practice in exposing identifiers, and what they refer to, within metadata. Not all metadata standards provide dedicated properties that make this clear and explicit.

Clarify: **clearly**?

Clarify: **explicitly**?

F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed (Essential)	FsF-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata of the object is retrievable programmatically through at least one of the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Structured data embedded in the landing page of the data object. ◦ Typed Links of metadata document or Signposting header links. ◦ Content negotiation with a PID provider service (e.g., DataCite).

‘Registered’ implies a *push* action by a repository, while ‘indexing’ implies a *pull* action by the resource discovery system- which could be the repository, or could be a search engine crawler over which the repository has no control. In a *push* scenario there may be more control over timely updates to information than in a *pull* scenario.

The RDA Indicator and the FAIRsFAIR metrics and tests address the exposure of metadata for harvesting or indexing by a machine. Neither address the criteria for what would be an acceptable ‘searchable resource’. Is it good enough to register metadata in a very obscure and specific resource restricted to a very small community? Should all resources be discoverable in major search engines? Should digital objects specific to a particular discipline or domain be discoverable by some list of search tools defined by their community? Would it be acceptable for disciplinary metadata to only be available in discipline-specific discovery systems? Do we envisage a registry of acceptable resource discovery systems?

CoreTrustSeal assessments would focus less on the machine-actionability and more on the availability of metadata about digital objects in a ‘searchable resource’ that meets the needs of the designated community.

To be Accessible:

Accessibility implies that some metadata has been accessed during the finding process, but it cannot imply that the data itself must be accessible to all (cf sensitive data). Accessibility implies a process for assessing the rights of the requester to gain access to the data and either granting access or justifying rejection.

A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-A1-01M Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data (Important)		Metadata includes the level of data access (e.g., public, embargoed, restricted) and its access conditions using appropriate metadata fields.
RDA-A1-02M Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention) (Essential)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access level metadata is machine-readable, and this is verified against controlled vocabularies:
RDA-A1-02D Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention) (Essential)	FsF-A1-01M Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	http://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/access_rights/
RDA-A1-03M Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record (Essential)	FsF-A1-02M Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	http://purl.org/eprint/accessRights
RDA-A1-03D Data identifier resolves to a digital object (Essential)	FsF-A1-03D Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right
RDA-A1-04M Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol (Essential)		The metadata / data URI's scheme is based on a shared application protocol. The metadata / data is accessible through the identifier provided.
RDA-A1-04D Data is accessible through standardised protocol (Essential)		
RDA-A1-05D Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program) (Important)		

Metadata and data may share an identifier as a single conceptual digital object. Metadata should be retrievable (resolvable?) via an identifier but circumstances (justified or unjustified) may mean that the data is not retrievable (cf: A2).

In the most open interpretation of a *communications protocol*, calling a repository on the telephone, quoting an identifier and receiving a copy of the data and metadata in the post would qualify as a communications protocol if both parties understand the inputs, outputs and parameters of the exchange. But for machine-actionable assessment more restrictive and specific technical systems must be defined.

The RDA Indicators address both human and machine access. The FAIRsFAIR metric additionally focuses on the availability of access condition metadata and specifies that these need to be verifiable against a defined set of controlled vocabularies.

Is there some element of standardisation that needs to be clarified? Is the communications protocol documented, approved, adopted, managed?

Do we envisage a registry of acceptable communications protocols?

Clarify: **communications protocol?**

Clarify: **standardized communications protocol?**

A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-A1.1-01M Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol (Essential)	<i>No associated FAIRsFAIR Metric</i>	<i>No associated FAIRsFAIR Test</i>
RDA-A1.1-01D Data is accessible through a free access protocol (Important)		

There is no associated FAIRsFAIR Metric or practical test in this case. The following open questions remain.

Does an open protocol mean an open source protocol or are there different requirements attached? Is the protocol free in the FOSS or FLOSS¹⁹ sense of the word? How can universality be defined? Which requirements or coverage should this entail? Who should be able to implement the protocol and how can we define whether something is implementable by that actor?

"Universally applicable" implies relatively simple integration by the community and therefore requires a wide distribution of the protocol. Web standards such as HTTP or HTTPS fulfill this requirement, which are also open standards supported by a number of free software packages.

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_and_open-source_software "The free-software movement and the open-source software movement are online social movements behind widespread production and adoption of FOSS, with the former preferring to use the terms FLOSS or free/libre"

Clarify: **open?**

Clarify: **free?**

Clarify: **universally?**

Clarify: **implementable?**

Clarify: **universally implementable?**

A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-A1.2-01D Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation (Useful)	<i>No associated FAIRsFAIR Metric</i>	<i>No associated FAIRsFAIR Test</i>

There is no associated FAIRsFAIR Metric or practical test in this case. The following issues remain open.

The Principle is a good starting point to ensure that digital objects, and the repositories that hold them, are not penalised for a perceived lack of openness. It is helpful to acknowledge that some digital objects must be protected for legal and ethical reasons.

Is it reasonable to assume that *some* metadata **must** always be available without an authentication/authorisation procedure?

How do we define the acceptable scope of 'necessary' within the boundaries of FAIR?

E.g.

- Sensitive personal data only accessible to approved users (OK)
- Restricting data access to minimise sharing without having a legal or ethical reason (Not OK)

Clarify: **where necessary?**

A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-A2-01M Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available (Essential)	FsF-A2-01M Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programmatic assessment of the preservation of metadata of a data object can only be tested if the object is deleted or replaced. So this test is only applicable for deleted, replaced or obsolete objects. Importantly, continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice. Therefore, we regard that the assessment of metric applies to at the level of a repository, not at the level of individual objects. For this reason, we excluded its assessment details from the F-UJI implementation.

This Principle meets the 'principle' that principles should be empirically demonstrable, but has been excluded from the practical tests under FAIRsFAIR. One could meet this principle by ensuring that the metadata remains accessible 'somewhere', but to be practically useful the old identifiers should continue to function and resolve to a 'tombstone' location .

Would it be reasonable to require that any persistent identifiers they have minted continue to resolve to some relevant information (e.g. Landing page) or, at a minimum, that the PID resolves to the metadata record (e.g. DataCite)?

This is the only FAIR Principle that has an explicit 'time' dimension and strongly implies the need for a repository or other data service provider that will ensure the 'preservation' of metadata even in cases where the data is no longer available²⁰.

Clarify: **accessible**?

To be Interoperable:

Interoperable between?

²⁰ L'Hours, Hervé, Kleemola, Mari, von Stein, Ilona, van Horik, René, Herterich, Patricia, Davidson, Joy, Rouchon, Olivier, Mokrane, Mustapha, & Huber, Robert. (2022). FAIR + Time: Preservation for a Designated Community (02.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797776>

I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-I1-01M Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardized format (Important)	FsF-I1-01M Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	<p><i>The metadata of the object is available in a formal knowledge representation language, e.g., through at least one of the following mechanisms:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Parsable, structured data is embedded in the landing page</i> • <i>Parsable, formal metadata (e.g., RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint.</i>
RDA-I1-02M Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation (Important)		
RDA-I1-01D Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format (Important)		
RDA-I1-02D Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation (Important)		

The RDA Indicators here set expectations for data, while the FAIRsFAIR metrics focus on metadata. In cases where the data of a digital object is not directly accessible it is impractical for a machine to test whether it uses standardised ‘semantic artefacts’ such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies. The FAIRsFAIR practical tests focus on identifying a narrow set of acceptable technologies that support standardised structured metadata.

Do we envisage a registry where semantic artefacts / knowledge representations are indexed based on the criteria set by the FAIR Principles (formal, accessible, shared, broadly applicable)? How would these criteria be formalised and who would be responsible for keeping such a registry up to date? How would the ‘sharedness’ of a semantic artefact be tracked? No complete, authoritative, cross-domain registry for semantic resources exists but several initiatives are working in this area (e.g. <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/> , <https://fairsharing.org> , <https://lod-cloud.net/>)

Clarify: **formal**

Clarify: **accessible**

Clarify: **shared**

Clarify: **broadly applicable**

Clarify: **language for knowledge representation**

I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-I2-01M Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies (Important)	<i>No associated FAIRsFAIR Metric (FsF-I2-01M Metadata uses semantic resources.)</i>	<i>Namespaces of known semantic resources are present in the metadata of an object; exclude common namespaces (e.g., rdf, rdfs, xsd, owl) from the test.</i>
RDA-I2-01D Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies (Useful)		

There is no associated FAIRsFAIR Metric but practical tests for FsF-I2-01M ('Metadata uses semantic resources') relate to this principle and most likely will be relabelled accordingly. The following issues remain open.

The implied coverage here is semantic artefacts such as controlled vocabularies (CV) and ontologies applied by both data and metadata. When research (meta) data includes values taken from a controlled vocabulary or ontology then they become dependent on that CV or ontology as a related digital object. If that dependent object is not itself FAIR then this may impact the FAIRness of the research (meta)data.

It is not yet clear whether the FAIR Principles are expected to be applied identically to vocabularies as they are to other digital object data and metadata, but there is a clear implication that, as for FAIR objects in FAIR enabling repositories, we need to define expectations for the curation and preservation of semantic artefacts. To be eligible as 'FAIR' would controlled vocabularies need to be assessed and certified through some form of standards-compliance process?

I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
<p>RDA-I3-01M Metadata includes references to other metadata (Important)</p> <p>RDA-I3-02M Metadata includes references to other data (Useful)</p> <p>RDA-I3-01D Data includes references to other data (useful)</p> <p>RDA-I3-02D Data includes qualified references to other data (Useful)</p> <p>RDA-I3-03M Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata (Important)</p> <p>RDA-I3-04M Metadata include qualified references to other data (Useful)</p>	<p>FsF-I3-01M Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata captures the relation between a data object and its related entity. • The relation is expressed using a relation type according to PROV-O or DataCite relation types. • Relations are preferably be expressed as actionable unique or persistent identifiers

The RDA Indicators expand the Principle out into all its potential components.

- Metadata to metadata
- Data to data
- And between data and metadata

The FAIRsFAIR metric compresses these back down because once the target object is set, the next step is to programmatically identify whether the metadata provided contains links to other persistently identified entities where there is a formally defined 'relationship'.

At this stage this evaluation is a binary outcome with no way of identifying whether the relationships are accurate or of value to (meta)data users unless these relations are provenance related.

Clarify: **qualified references**

Clarify: **other metadata**

To be Reusable:

Reusable by?

R1. meta(data)²¹ are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
RDA-R1-01M Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse (Essential)	FsF-R1-01MD Metadata specifies the content of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metadata includes the type of the object and the technical properties of its data file such as format, size, observed or measured variables.• Metadata values of the properties comply with the actual data file.

The sentiment of the Principle is clear and justified, but there are a range of areas where clarification is needed and these may depend on context. For example whether the (meta)data are rich, plural (sufficiently broad and granular) and relevant seems to depend on whether a “domain-relevant community standard” can be identified, this implies a registry of standards associated with domains, communities (disciplines), which are all indexed against these criteria.

The FAIRsFAIR metric focuses on the specification of data content within the metadata. The practical tests seek to identify the technical properties claimed for the objects (within the metadata) and to validate these against the underlying data file(s).

Clarify: **richly**

Clarify: **plurality**

Clarify: **accurate**

Clarify: **relevant**

Are we dependent on the domain-relevant community standards (R1.3) to provide the context which would offer clarification here? Is such a standard also a dependency for R1.1 and R1.2.?

²¹ The reference here to “meta(data)” is in contrast to “(meta) data” elsewhere.

R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
<p>RDA-R1.1-01M Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused (Essential)</p> <p>RDA-R1.1-02M Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence (Important)</p> <p>RDA-R1.1-03M Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence (Important)</p>	<p>FsF-R1.1-01M Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata contains license information represented using an appropriate metadata element. • A standard, machine readable license is specified.

Both the metadata and data must have usage (rights) information accessible to the user at the point of use.

The RDA Indicators seek a reuse licence that is standard-compliant and machine-understandable. The FAIRsFAIR practical tests evaluate the presence of licence information by checking a [set of] possible metadata elements.

Clarify: **clear**

Clarify: **accessible**

Clarify: **data usage licence**

R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
<p>RDA-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards (Important)</p> <p>RDA-R1.2-02M Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language (Useful)</p>	<p>FsF-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata includes properties representing data creation such as creator, contributors, creation and modification dates and version, source, and relations that indicate data creation activities. • Provenance metadata is available in a machine-readable version of PROV-O or PAV

Both the metadata and data must identify which activity they are generated by/used by and which human actor/machine/agent they are attributed to. The RDA Indicators specify the need for community-based standards and language, while the FAIRsFAIR tests focus on the machine-readability of the properties. The FAIRsFAIR metrics also make suggestions for which properties to include. Can these be clarified at the generic level or are they dependent on local context? In one environment, defining the author and publisher might be sufficiently detailed provenance. In another environment a detailed history of all derived objects and which agents and processes generated them may be required to ensure trust in the resultant data.

Clarify: **detailed**

Clarify: **provenance**

R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

RDA Indicator	FAIRsFAIR Metric	FAIRsFAIR Practical Test
<p>RDA-R1.3-01M Metadata complies with a community standard (Essential)</p> <p>RDA-R1.3-02M Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard (Essential)</p>	<p>FsF-R1.3-01M Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata is available through at least one of the domain metadata standards listed in RDA Metadata Standards Catalogue
<p>RDA-R1.3-01D Data complies with a community standard (Essential)</p> <p>RDA-R1.3-02D Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard (Important)</p>	<p>FsF-R1.3-02D Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is available in a long-term file format as defined in ISO/TR 22299 • Data is available in an open format (see e.g., https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_open_formats) • Data is available in a scientific file format (see e.g., Library of Congress dataset formats, Wolfram Alpha supported file formats)

This principle indicates that we must either clarify terms at a generic level and apply them to the full range of (meta)data scenarios, or we must acknowledge that clarification is only possible with further contextual information. Community standards could include approved file formats, approved metadata schemas or detailed instructions on how objects should be structured. This implies a need to define domain-relevant communities and to define the level of formality needed to ‘approve’ their standards. It certainly implies a need for a (FAIR) registry of such standards.

Clarify: **domain**

Clarify: **domain-relevant**

Clarify: **community**

Clarify: **standards**